

The NIH Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics Data Hub (RADx Data Hub) system owned by the NIH Office of Data Science Strategy (ODSS) provides information and data resources for scientific research. The RADx Data Hub User Code of Conduct sets forth principles for responsible management and use of RADx Data Hub data through access from the database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP). Users of the RADx Data Hub agree to comply with all terms of the User Code of Conduct, including investigators who are approved by NIH to access data. Failure to abide by any term within this User Code of Conduct may result in revocation of approved access to data obtained through dbGaP and the RADx Data Hub. Users of the RADx Data Hub agree to:

1. Use data solely in connection with the research project described in the approved Data Access Request
2. Preserve and protect the confidentiality of the data, and not sell or distribute the data to any entity or individual beyond those specified in the approved Data Access Request
3. Establish safeguards to prevent unauthorized viewing or release of RADx Data Hub information or data
4. Make no attempt to identify or contact individual participants, households, or groups from whom data were collected, or generate information that could allow participants' identities to be readily ascertained, without appropriate approvals from the submitting institutions
5. Data available in the RADx Data Hub (access through dbGaP) are provided without warranty or liability of any kind
6. Notify the RADx Data Hub Administrator (RADx-DataHub@nih.gov) of any errors discovered in the data
7. Ensure personal data submitted by you are accurate to the best of your knowledge and kept up to date by you
8. Acknowledge that your data may be used for administrative management of the RADx Data Hub and for reporting purposes with the goal of improving services offered by the RADx Data Hub
9. Provide appropriate acknowledgment in any dissemination of research findings including the investigator(s) who generated the data, the funding source, accession number(s) of the data, and the dbGaP and RADx Data Hub repository from which the data were accessed
10. Adhere to the dbGaP Data Use Certification Agreement and ensure that only approved users can gain access to data file